

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF USING THE TRIZ (THEORY OF INVENTIVE PROBLEM SOLVING) PROGRAM IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION LESSONS

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ANNOTATSIYA

Maktabgacha ta'lim-tarbiyada yosh bolalarni ixtirochilik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish hamisha dolzarb mavzulardan biri hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolada bog'cha bolalarining mashg'ulotlarida TRIZ dasturini qo'llagan holda, bolalarning ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishning zamonaviy shakl, usul, metodlari haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ijodiy fikr, qobilyat, ta'lim, sinf, dars.

ABSTRACT

Development of inventive abilities of young children in preschool education is always one of the most relevant topics. This article talks about modern forms, methods and methods of developing children's creative abilities using the TRIZ program in the classes of kindergarten children.

Keywords: Creative thinking, ability, education, class, lesson.

Emergence of the TRIZ program.

The TRIZ program appeared in the middle of the 20th century, and at first it was even pedagogic was not related to In 1946, former Soviet engineer, scientist and science fiction writer Heinrich Altshuller began to study the methods most used by inventors. During this time, it acquired new algorithms, and in the early 80s, pedagogues took it as a basis for experimental classes and teaching methods in schools.

The purpose of TRIZ pedagogy.

The goal of TRIZ pedagogy is to develop flexible thinking and imagination, the ability to solve complex problems skillfully and effectively. In modern pedagogy, the

TRIZ program is an innovative solution for unique ways of working with students, unusual teaching techniques and achieving high results.

Time does not stand still. Time is always in motion, creating the ground for new generations to emerge. Recently, we have been hearing terms such as indigo children, new intellects, and hyperactive children. Of course, this is not in vain. This is what the world is leading today.

It is not an exaggeration to say that the gene pool of the future generation is the active development of children's mental abilities from preschool age. The work to be done in this regard is clearly defined in the "state requirements for the development of children of primary and preschool age" of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Reforms in the preschool education system, which are becoming more and more popular today, are undoubtedly based on the requirements of this state.

Of course, many effective methods are used in preschool education. One such method is the TRIZ method. The TRIZ method came to our country in the 50s of the last century thanks to the efforts of the famous Russian scientist, writer, inventor Henrikh Saulovich Alshuller.

In this, the two main rules of teaching - the relationship between the teacher and the child occupy the main place. The TRIZ method makes it possible to teach and educate a child under the motto "creativity in everything".

Teaching children of preschool age consists in teaching children to search and think independently. The main task of TRIZ is not to find solutions to problems, but to find answers to vital questions. Children are asked questions in the TRIZ method and their unique antique answers are heard.

For example; When 5-year-old children are asked about liquid and solid substances, they give the following answers:

- The liquid passes through the pipe, we can put it in a glass.
- They answered that you can step on a liquid substance, but if you step on a solid substance, you can injure your leg.

The following TRIZ methods can be used in kindergarten;

What do we do to avoid getting wet in the rain?

- Why do we get sick?

By finding answers to these questions, children's logical thinking, perception, memory, imagination, and speech become active, and the stock of information expands.

Educational games based on TRIZ- mental development method.

We will also talk about the game "princess who does not laugh" for children of the middle group.

Rules of the game: everyone listens quietly, children take turns to show their creativity, support each other, come up with new ideas to please the princess. Children sit on chairs in a circle. A sad little girl dressed like a princess sits in the middle;

Educator:

- Children, why is our princess sad? Who will do what to please our queen?
- For example; I will tell a poem to our princess"- the educator tells a poem about children.

One child tells riddles, another tells a song, another tells a story. In this, the child's creativity increases. So, all the children show their creativity and make the princess happy.

The TRIZ method develops children's moral qualities, such as joy of success, desire to help, and the desire to find a way out of a difficult situation. The TRIZ method has a great role in the moral formation of preschool children. For example; "Good – bad", "What could it be?", "Change yourself", "Why is it sad?" on the basis of such games, it is possible to raise children's moral indicators by encouraging children to think and determining their results.

In this case, the educator should use visual activity as the main component in teaching creative thinking in children based on TRIZ. In this, children's range of ideas is enriched, their vocabulary grows, and their creative abilities develop.

Preschool age is unique. Because with the formation of the child, his life and intelligence begin to improve. It is of great importance to further develop the current field of pre-school education, to effectively use the TRIZ method in the comprehensive and high-quality preparation of children for school education.

In conclusion, it can be said that the TRIZ method can become an important factor in the formation of a real gene pool in society.

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